

Carbon-carbon bond formation via palladium catalyzed reactions of organomercurials with acylhalides

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Manuscript received 7 December 2006, accepted 27 February 2007

Abstract : The palladium catalyzed acyldemetallation reactions of methyl mercury iodide provide a mild, selective and general method for the construction of new C–C bond i.e. for the synthesis of unsymmetrical ketone. The reaction proceeds in acetone, in the presence of a nucleophilic catalyst (iodide ion), at room temperature. The catalytic cycle involved in the reaction consists of a sequence of oxidative addition, transmetalation and reductive elimination steps. The role played by the iodide ion as a nucleophilic catalyst is discussed.

Keywords : Palladium catalysis, acyldemetallation reactions, organomercurials.

C–C bond formation reactions are important reactions in organic synthesis. A number of excellent reviews have been published which covers different aspects of synthetic processes and transition metal based homogeneous catalysis used in C–C bond formation¹. Among the transition metals, palladium has a well-established chemistry in (0), (II) and (IV) oxidation states and therefore it is widely used as a versatile tool in catalytic organic synthesis².

Palladium catalyzed acyldemetallation reactions of diorganomercurials with acyl halides, and carbonylation reactions of alkylmercury halide with aryl halides, were carried out for the synthesis of unsymmetrical ketones in high yield³. The low reactivity of organomercurials was easily overcome by transition metal and nucleophilic catalysis.

In the present communication, we report palladium catalyzed acyldemetallation reactions of methyl mercury iodide with acyl halides as an important route for the synthesis of acetophenones (Reaction 1). The reaction proceeds selectively in acetone, in the presence of iodide ion as the nucleophilic catalyst; at room temperature to give 70–80% yield (isolated) of the product.

Catalyst : $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CN})_2$

R = C_6H_5 , $p\text{-FC}_6\text{H}_4$, $p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$, $p\text{-BrC}_6\text{H}_4$ and $p\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$

I⁻ = NaI

Results and discussion

A number of experiments were performed to optimize the reaction conditions by changing concentration of iodide ion.

We found that, the reaction proceeds selectively in the presence of Pd catalyst [$\text{PdCl}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CN})_2$] and iodide ion (2 equivalent of iodide ion based on Hg) in acetone to give 70–80% yield of the product. The results are summarized in Table 1. The catalytic cycle involved in the reaction is depicted in Scheme 1. Pd^0 is generated in the reaction mixture under reaction conditions. The catalytic cycle involves a sequence of oxidative addition, transmetalation and reductive elimination steps³. RCOI oxidatively adds to Pd^0 and gives RCOPdI complex (step a). RCOPdI then undergoes transmetalation with CH_3HgI to give RCOPdCH_3 complex (step b). RCOPdCH_3 further reductively eliminates RCOCH_3 with the recovery of Pd^0 (step c).

Iodide ion plays an important role in acyldemetallation reaction (Scheme 2)³. It performs several functions : (i) Transformation of acylchloride into acyliodide, which is reactive in oxidative addition step. (ii) With CH₃HgI, iodide ion forms an ionic complex (CH₃HgI₂)⁻ and therefore heterolytic fission of C–Hg bond becomes easier in transmetallation step. (iii) It forms an ionic complex (Pd⁰I)⁻ with Pd⁰ and hence precipitation of Pd black does not take place.

Scheme 2

Conclusion :

The reaction of CH₃HgI with RCOCl, in the presence of palladium catalyst and excess of iodide ion (nucleophilic catalyst), in acetone provides a mild and selective method for the synthesis of acetophenone or substituted acetophenones in high yields.

Table 1. Reactions of CH₃HgI with RCOCl [acetone, catalyst (1 mol %), NaI (2 equivalent based on Hg)] at room temperature

Entry no.	R	Catalyst	Reaction time (min)	% Yield (isolated) RCOCH ₃
1.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	A	20	80
2.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	A	30	78
3.	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	A	30	75
4.	<i>p</i> -FC ₆ H ₄	A	30	78
5.	C ₆ H ₅	A	30	73

A – PdCl₂(C₆H₅CN)₂

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Palladium catalysts PdCl₂(C₆H₅CN)₂ (Acros Chemicals), and CH₃HgI (Alfa Aesar Chemicals) were used. NaI was dried under vacuum for two hours before use. Acetone was purified as per standard procedures and distilled before use.

IR spectra of the products were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 883 spectrophotometer in the range 4000–600 cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian 300 MHz spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as the internal standard

Acyldemetallation reaction :

The reaction was carried out in 10 ml RB flask. 4 ml of acetone, 2 mmol of NaI, 1 mmol acyl halide, 1 mmol of CH₃HgI and 0.01 mmol of catalyst (1 mol %) were placed in the flask and the slurry was stirred vigorously at room temperature. The completion of reaction was tested by TLC. The reaction mixture was then diluted by adding 10 ml water and extracted with 3 × 5 ml ether. The ether solutions were combined and washed with 2 × 5 ml of aqueous solutions of NaI to remove traces of mercury salt from the organic layer. The ether layer was then dried over MgSO₄ and evaporated to get corresponding acetophenone.

The physical constants and spectral (IR and NMR) data of acetophenone and substituted acetophenones obtained are in accordance with the published data⁴.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (PGM) is thankful to UGC, New Delhi for the award of Major research project. The authors are also grateful to authorities of Solapur University, Solapur and Shivaji University, Kolhapur for providing research facilities.

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